

Tonolli Memorial Award

The Tonolli Fund of SIL was created in 1985 through a bequest from Vittorio and Livia Tonolli, well known limnologists at the Istituto Italiano di Idrobiologia in Pallanza, Italy. The purpose of the fund is to provide assistance to young limnologists in developing countries and encourage them to join SIL. Information about the fund can be found at LIMNOLOGY.ORG/tonolli-memorial-award. Below are two reports from recent Tonolli Fund recipients.

Carmela Vicera (Philippines)

Chitinoclastic *Aeromonas* sp. from planktonic copepods in Lake Taal, Philippines

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Approximately 10¹¹ metric tons of chitin are produced annually, and biodegradation of this insoluble polymer is important in the nutrient cycling in lakes. In freshwater ecosystems much of the chitin is derived from crustaceans (Cauchie, 2002; Köllner *et al.*, 2012), and one of the best initiators of its biodegradation are bacteria. These chitinoclastic microorganisms are thought to be responsible for the mineralization of approximately 93% of the chitin in freshwater environments and have been estimated to represent circa 1% of all prokaryotes in aquatic environments (Beier *et al.*, 2011). They can be found in sediments, in the water column, and even as bacterial communities associated with plants and animals. We wanted to investigate other niches where we can possibly isolate these microorganisms, and this led us to delve deeper into the freshwater copepods in Lake Taal, Philippines.

Copepods are small multicellular crustaceans that can be found within the water column and on sediments in both marine and freshwater habitats. They can support distinct bacterial communities and thus they play an important role in the overall microbial diversity and functions of distinct microhabitats (Tang *et al.*, 2010). Commonly, the bacteria in copepods are found attached to egg sacs, and their oral and anal region where presumably the release of nutrients is high. In lakes, several studies on calanoid and cyclopoid copepods have revealed that both these groups harbor distinct bacterial communities. To have a glimpse of the microbiology of copepods in a tropical lake, we endeavored to isolate and identify the cultivable chitinolytic bacteria associated with copepods

Fig. 1 Open water sampling site in Lake Taal, Philippines.

in Lake Taal (Fig. 1 and 2).

Copepods are the most abundant zooplankton in Lake Taal, making up 64% and 84% of the zooplankton abundance and the total biomass, respectively, over different seasons (Papa *et al.*, 2011). When these copepods die or molt, their exoskeletons tend to accumulate in the lake therefore the ability of chitinoclastic bacteria to hydrolyze this chitinous exoskeleton is vital to lake-wide carbon cycling. In fact, the degraded exoskeletons release dissolved organic nutrients in the surrounding water that are made available for other organisms. This shows the importance of chitin degrading bacteria in the initiation of carbon cycling in the aquatic ecosystem.

Six individuals each of the cyclopoid (*Mesocyclops ogunnus* (Onabamiro, 1957) and calanoid (*Arctodiaptomus dorsalis* (Marsh, 1907) were sampled. Extreme variability in the heterotrophic bacterial load was seen for each individual copepod species, where bacterial counts ranging from $\sim 1 \times 10^3$ – 1×10^5 were recorded. From the 12 copepod individuals, a total of 81 bacteria were isolated: 44 from calanoids and 37 from cyclopoids. Colloidal chitin plate agar assay showed that 9 out of 81 isolates demonstrated chitinoclastic activity, six of which were isolated from the cyclopoids and three from calanoids. Using 16s rRNA

gene sequencing analysis, these bacteria were identified as *Aeromonas* sp. *Aeromonas hydrophyla*, *A. caviae*, *A. ichthiosmia*, *A. jandei* were recovered from cyclopoids, while *A. veronii* and *A. fluvialis* were from calanoids. Interestingly, *A. dhakensis* was found on both copepods.

Aeromonas is a very good producer of the enzyme chitinase (Hiraga *et al.*, 2014). In environments where some bacteria are not able to survive, this versatile genus can easily adapt and produce metabolic enzymes for survival.

We further investigated the ability of this bacterial group to degrade chitin when environmental

Fig. 2 Fish cages near sampling site in Lake Taal.

conditions are altered. We found that isolates from both copepods favor an alkaline pH, temperatures ranging from 28-35°C, a low salinity concentration of 0.85‰, and peptone as nitrogen source. These results reveal that *Aeromonas* are capable of degrading chitin using both organic and inorganic carbon source and in a wide range of pH and temperature, suggesting that the different species of this group of bacteria easily adapt to the environmental changes in the lake, allowing them to produce chitin-degrading enzymes even under unfavorable conditions.

This study was able to show the presence of chitinoclastic *Aeromonas* on copepods present in Lake Taal. Although we have not fully identified the bacterial community for each copepod species, we believe that this study can influence other researchers to further explore the bacterial community of copepod species in Philippine lakes. To our knowledge this microbiological study is the first to be done for copepods in Lake Taal, and this would not have been possible without the aid of the Tonolli Memorial Fund.

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Effect of zooplankton, macrophytes and piscivorous fish in the control of *Microcystis* spp. (cyanobacteria): mesocosm experiments

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Cyanobacterial blooms are one of the main problems in urban water bodies, especially when these are refilled using partially treated wastewater as is the case for several ponds, lakes and canals in Mexico City (Figueroa-Sánchez *et al.*, 2014; 2020). These blooms affect the water quality, aquatic biota and the people who use these sites for recreation. This is the case in the rowing and canoeing canal "Virgilio Uribe" (RCC) an artificial, eutrophic water body (Gayosso-Morales *et al.* 2018) affected by *Microcystis* blooms throughout the year. The canal provides refuge to migratory or partially migratory birds such pelicans, storks and coots. The canal also has a small colony of the endemic but highly endangered Axolotl (*Ambystoma*

a mixture of the green algae *Chlorella vulgaris* and *Scenedesmus acutus* for more than a year before experimentation.

Typha latifolia was available in the RCC. Juvenile stage macrophytes (1.5 m) extracted from the root were washed and used. Subsequently, the plants were placed in 20 L containers with RCC water previously filtered through a 90 µm mesh size. All the above was carried out 48 h before setting up the experiment. *Goodea atripinnis* (1.5 ± 0.05 cm total length) were captured from the RCC using homemade traps made with PET (1 L) nasa-type bottles. The fish were kept in a 20 L tank containing unfiltered water from the RCC. The fish were fed *S. cf mixtus* every 2 days prior to experimentation. *Petenia splendida* (14±1cm), a piscivorous fish were acquired from Acuapets aquaculture fish farm in the State of Tabasco and transferred to Mexico City.

For both experiments sixteen cylindrical aluminum frames covered with transparent polyethylene to form closed containers (45 cm diameter, 60cm length and 80L capacity) were employed (Figure 1). Each was filled with 70 L of previously filtered (mesh size 200 and 90 µm) water from the site. Mixed population of *S. cf mixtus* (5 ind./ L) was added to the mesocosms from a previously established laboratory culture. A bunch of *T. latifolia* (600 g) was added to the treatments (T). We also introduced three individuals of *G. atripinnis* (2 cm) previously

Fig. 1 Mesocosm set up in the RCC and the first author at the study site.

mexicanum), and the native acocil crayfish.

Research on biomanipulation in tropical and subtropical systems is relatively new. For the RCC, we hypothesized that the abundance of the cladoceran *Simocephalus*, a crustacean species capable of surviving on *Microcystis* (Nandini and Rao, 1998) will increase in the absence of the omnivorous fish *Goodea atripinnis* (Goodeidae), while the presence of the macrophyte *Typha latifolia* will provide shelter to the cladoceran against fish predation and promote the decrease of nutrients, resulting in a decrease in cyanobacteria. On the other hand, the abundance of *Simocephalus* would increase in the presence of the piscivorous fish *Petenia splendida* due to its predation on *Goodea atripinnis*.

To test this, we isolated *Simocephalus cf mixtus* from a canal in Lake Xochimilco and cultured them in 30L containers in aerated tap water and

captured from the site. In treatments with the piscivorous fish, one *P. splendida* (Ps) (14±1cm) per container was introduced. Four replicates per treatment were set up. The mesocosms were placed inside the canal, firmly tied so as to avoid tilting from wind or wave action. Observations and sampling were carried out for 16 days.

Zooplankton species were quantified; cladocerans were counted and subsequently returned to each treatment while rotifers and copepods were filtered using a mesh of 50 µm and fixed in 4% formalin for later analysis. *Microcystis* spp. were quantified as individuals or colonies per ml. For both sets of experiments, chlorophyll (Figure 2), largely contributed by *Microcystis* sp. declined with the presence of *Simocephalus* and *Typha*. The presence of fish, omnivores or piscivores, resulted in a decline in the cladoceran density and thereby an increase